

A Synthesis of 5-hydroxy-2-methoxybenzoic Acid.

BY ANDREW NORMAN MELDRUM AND MADHAVLAL SUKHLAL SHAH.

Sulphosalicylic acid which the authors have shown to be 5-sulpho-2-hydroxybenzoic (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1986 ; *cf.* Stewart, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2555) might be expected, on fusion with potassium hydroxide, to give 2:5-dihydroxybenzoic acid (I). Remsen, however, found that sulphosalicylic acid on fusion with potash gave salicylic acid and phenol (*Annalen*, 1875, 179, 107). In repeated experiments with the methyl ether of sulphosalicylic acid the authors had a similar experience: fusion with potassium hydroxide, sodium hydroxide, sodium methylate and sodium acetate gave salicylic acid as the principal product in each case.

The synthesis of 5-hydroxy-2-methoxybenzoic acid was undertaken with a view to recognising it in case it should be formed in the fusion experiments. The difficulty in preparing it was noted by Tiemann and Maxmüller (*Ber.*, 1881, 14, 1985). It cannot be obtained by the direct methylation of gentisic acid, 2:5-dihydroxybenzoic acid, because the tendency is to produce the 5-methoxy- and 2:5-dimethoxybenzoic acids.

(I)

(II)

Emil Fischer, starting with gentisic acid, by using methylchloroformate, obtained 5-carbomethoxy-2-hydroxybenzoic acid (II) (*Ber.*, 1909, 42 215). Emil Fischer and Pfeiffer treated this substance with diazo-methane obtaining methyl-5-carbomethoxy-2-methoxybenzoate which on hydrolysis, gave 5-hydroxy-2-methoxybenzoic acid: the acid melted at 155°-56° and gave a greyish violet coloration with ferric chloride solution (*Annalen*, 1912, 389, 198). The authors have obtained the acid from the 5-amino-compound and find

that it melts at 172° and gives with ferric chloride solution a violet coloration that intensifies on standing.

When the methyl ether of salicylic acid was nitrated, two isomeric nitro-acids were produced which were separated by means of their barium and calcium salts ; the procedure was similar to that adopted by Simonsen and Rau (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 220). Froelicher and Cohen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1652) describe three isomeric acids as the products of nitration in presence of acetic anhydride. The authors* find that nitration at different temperatures produces only the 5- and 3-nitro-2-methoxybenzoic acids and that a low temperature, leads to a high percentage of 5-nitro-acid.

5-Nitro-2-methoxybenzoic acid was reduced by ammoniacal ferrous hydroxide (Simonsen and Rau, *loc. cit.*). Froelicher and Cohen (*loc. cit.*) regard ferrous hydroxide as unsatisfactory and recommend the use of stannous chloride: the authors find that ammoniacal ferrous hydroxide reduces the acid smoothly and gives an 89 per cent. yield of the amino-sulphate.

Numerous attempts were made to diazotise the amino-sulphate and then to obtain a phenol without isolation of the diazo-compound but those were unsuccessful. It was thought advisable to isolate the diazo-compound and then to work carefully with it.

The diazo-sulphate, on separation, was found to possess properties that accounted for the difficulties already encountered in converting it into a phenol. It is unusually stable at 150°; it swells and decomposes. It can be preserved in a blue coloured bottle or a black envelope without decomposition. The solution in water when boiled in absence of light did not decompose and on exposure to light produced a red coloured tar. Finally the substance was converted into a phenol by heating it using fused magnesium chloride as a medium.

The 5-hydroxy-2-methoxybenzoic acid thus obtained melts at 172°, the isomer, 5-methoxy-2-hydroxybenzoic acid, melts at 142°. It was converted into 2:5-dimethoxybenzoic acid melting at 80°. Tiemann and Maxmüller (*loc. cit.*) gave 76°. Emil Fischer and Pfeiffer did not carry out the methylation of their acid melting at 155-56°.

* Dr. J. N. Rây informs us that in 1925 he repeated this work of Froelicher and Cohen at Manchester and arrived at the same conclusion that only two nitro-derivatives were formed. But this result has not been published by him.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nitration of 2-Methoxybenzoic Acid.—To a solution of 2-methoxybenzoic acid (10 g.) in nitric acid (d 1.4, 25 g.) at 30°, sulphuric acid (30 g.) was added drop by drop ; the solution became orange coloured and some nitrogen peroxide was evolved. After 15 minutes the solution was treated with ice-water (300 c.c.) when a crystalline mass separated which was collected, washed and dried, yield, 13.5 g. It consists of two isomeric nitro-acids.

The two isomeric acids are not very different in solubility ; the barium and calcium salts of the 5-nitro-acid are much less soluble than those of the 3-nitro-acid ; the barium salt is less soluble than the calcium salt. The mixture of acids was repeatedly extracted with boiling water ; finally an acid was left undissolved which crystallised from dilute acetic acid in rectangular plates, m.p. 162-63°, yield, 5 g. This is 5-nitro-2-methoxybenzoic acid. The aqueous solution of the two acids was digested with barium carbonate. The solution gave glossy straw coloured needles in clusters of barium 5-nitro-2-methoxybenzoate. When the latter salt no longer separated, the mother-liquor was acidified and the precipitated acids were collected. On digestion of these acids with water and calcium carbonate, a solution of the calcium salts was obtained from which calcium 5-nitro-2-methoxybenzoate separated in prismatic needles.

The barium and calcium salts together were dissolved in water and the solution was acidified. The 5-nitro-acid that separated, was crystallised from water, m.p. 162-63°, yield, 5.3 g. (Found: Equi. wt., 196.9. $C_8H_7O_5N$ requires equi. wt., 197.0).

The mother-liquor, when it ceased to give the calcium salt, was acidified. The 3-nitro-acid that separated was crystallised from water in silky needles, m.p. 196°, yield, 3 g. (Found: Equi. wt., 197.2. $C_8H_7O_5N$ requires equi. wt., 197.0).

It was observed that the proportion of 3-nitro acid increases if nitration is carried out at a higher temperature.

Temp.	5-Nitro-acid.	3-Nitro-acid.
0° (Simonsen and Rau)	83 p.c.	14 p. c.
30-35°	76	22
75-100°	73	25

5-Amino-sulphate-2-methoxybenzoic Acid.—5-Nitro-2-methoxybenzoic acid was reduced by ammoniacal ferrous hydroxide. As this process was found unsatisfactory by Froelicher and Cohen (*loc. cit.*) it is given in detail.

5-Nitro-2-methoxybenzoic acid (40 g.) dissolved in ammonia solution, was treated with a solution of ferrous sulphate (320 g.) in water (700 c.c.); ammonia in excess was then added and the mixture vigorously shaken when it changed colour and finally became yellowish green. The mixture was then heated on a water-bath for two hours and allowed to stand overnight. The ferric hydroxide was removed by filtration and washed with boiling water. The pink coloured filtrate was concentrated, treated with animal charcoal and filtered; the filtrate on acidification with sulphuric acid deposited glistening square plates which did not melt but decomposed at 242°, yield, 38.5 g. With ferric chloride solution the pure amino-sulphate developed a violet coloration which intensified on standing. (Found: N, 6.41; S, 7.25. $(C_8H_9O_3N)_2 H_2SO_4$ requires N, 6.48; S, 7.4 per cent.).

5-Diazo-sulphate-2-methoxybenzoic Acid.—The finely powdered amino-sulphate (20 g.) was suspended in 10 per cent. sulphuric acid (30 c. c.) cooled and treated with a stream of nitrous acid gas under constant shaking, the mixture being kept below 10°. The amino-sulphate passed into solution and the process was stopped when a trace of it was left undissolved. Air was then bubbled through the solution to remove undissolved nitrous gases. After filtration the solution was poured into absolute alcohol (250 c. c.) and the whole immersed in a freezing mixture. 5-Diazo-sulphate-2-methoxybenzoic acid separated in rectangular plates which were collected, washed with cold absolute alcohol and dried, yield, 18.5 g.

The diazo-sulphate decomposes with evolution of nitrogen and carbon dioxide at 150°. On exposure to light it changes at the surface to a red substance. When kept in a black envelope or a blue coloured bottle it is perfectly stable. (Found: N, 12.5; S, 7.06. $(C_8H_7O_3N_2)_2 SO_4$ requires N, 12.34; S, 7.05 per cent.).

5-Hydroxy-2-methoxybenzoic Acid.—After several experiments the following process was adopted. $MgCl_2 \cdot 6 H_2O$ (200 g.) was placed in a casserole and heated to 145°; a solution of 5-diazo-sulphate-2-methoxybenzoic acid (8 g.) in water (15 c. c.) was then added drop by drop, keeping the mixture well-stirred. Nitrogen escaped freely and within a short time a pinkish white mass collect-

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ed on the surface. (Tarry products begin to separate if the mixture is not well-stirred and if the solution is added quickly). The whole mass was then heated for 15 minutes and the temperature allowed to rise to 155°. The mixture after cooling was dissolved in hot water and the solution was neutralised with ammonia, decolorised with animal charcoal and filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave needle-shaped crystals, yield, 1.8 g. For analysis the substance was recrystallised from hot water when it separated in glistening needles, m.p. 172°. The acid gave, with ferric chloride solution, a violet coloration that intensified on standing. It is easily soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and acetone and moderately soluble in benzene and toluene. (Found: C, 57.25; H, 4.65; equi. wt., 169.168. $C_8H_8O_4$ requires C, 57.1; H, 4.78 per cent; equi. wt., 168).

The *barium* salt is produced on digestion with water and barium carbonate, crystallises in tufts of needles containing 3 molecules of water. (Found: Ba, 25.96; H_2O , 10.52. $(C_8H_7O_4)_2 Ba, 3 H_2O$ requires Ba, 26.15; H_2O , 16.3 per cent.). The barium salt on treatment with the equivalent amount of sulphuric acid liberated the original acid which melted, when heated alone or mixed with the above specimen, at 172° and gave with ferric chloride solution a violet coloration that intensified on standing.

2:5-Dimethoxybenzoic Acid.—5-Hydroxy-2-methoxybenzoic acid (0.5 g.) was dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution and treated alternately with dimethylsulphate (8 c.c.) and 20 p. c. sodium hydroxide solution (25 c. c.). More sodium hydroxide (10 c. c.) was then added and the ester hydrolysed by heating on a water-bath. On cooling, sodium-2:5-dimethoxybenzoate separated in fibrous condition; it was collected, dissolved in hot water and acidified with hydrochloric acid. 2:5-Dimethoxybenzoic acid separated in shining needles, m.p. 80°, yield, 0.45 g. It was crystallised from water for analysis. (Found: Equi. wt., 182.9. $C_9H_{10}O_4$ requires equi. wt., 182).

Summary.

1. The synthesis of 5-hydroxy-2-methoxybenzoic acid has been accomplished from the corresponding amino-compound.
2. 5-Hydroxy-2-methoxybenzoic acid and 5-amino-sulphate-2-methoxybenzoic acid are found to give with ferric chloride solution a violet coloration which intensifies on standing.

3. A new method for converting an unusually stable diazo-compound into a phenol, namely treatment with fused magnesium chloride, is described.

Further work is in progress with a view (a) to account for the violet coloration which 5-amino and 5-hydroxy-2-methoxybenzoic acids produce with ferric chloride, and (b) to generalise the use of fused magnesium chloride in the conversion of stable diazo-compounds into phenols.

THE MADHAVLAL RANCHHODLAL SCIENCE INSTITUTE,
GUJARAT COLLEGE, AHMEDABAD.

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